

PRACTICAL STUDY OF THE APPLICATION OF OZONE TECHNOLOGY FOR AGRICULTURAL PURPOSES IN INCREASING THE PRODUCTIVITY AND EFFICIENCY OF CEREALS

Janmammedova R.,

Hajiyev T.

National Aerospace Agency

Ecological Institute

Abstract

The article reflects the current trends in the application of ozone technology. Ozone is becoming increasingly popular at a time when there is a growing demand for pesticides, stimulants, antibiotics and other substances that are toxic to humans, and at a time when society is concerned about environmental safety in production technology. The use of technology is very important in increasing the profitability of agriculture.

Keywords: Ozone technology, ozonators, classification of ozonators, working principles, ozon generators, devices in drip irrigation system.

Introduction. One of the strategically important issues for the Republic of Azerbaijan is to increase the productivity and efficiency of agricultural production. Mains of protection of plants, seeds and finished agricultural products are especially important in increasing and maintaining agricultural productivity [1,2].

At the same time, the requirements for the protection and preservation of the natural environment, the reduction of fertilizers containing various pesticides and their quantity, and the improvement of the quality

of agricultural products have increased significantly. Thus, ozone technology is widely used in crop production, animal husbandry fishing, seed production and storage of products.

Therefore, it is necessary to increase the production of agricultural products, improve the quality of products and expand the use of modern ozone technologies in solving problems arising in their storage.

Object of research. Pirshaghi settlement of Absheron district.

Space picture 1. 2020 –years

Result of research. The results of a detailed analysis of external experience have shown that ozone plays a positive role in increasing productivity and efficiency by having a positive effect on seed multiplication, plant growth and development. Numerous studies and practical results have proved that the application of ozone technologies in agriculture is justified.

Materials and methods. Prospects for the use of ozone in agriculture are due to its antibacterial

properties as well as the environmental friendliness of ozone, safety, universality, economy and ease of use. Ozone is becoming more and more popular at a time when there is a growing demand for pesticides, stimulants, antibiotics and other substances that are toxic to humans, and society is concerned about the environmental cleanliness of crop production technology.

Application of water ozonation devices in drip irrigation systems.

KP5. B1

KP20. B9

KP10.B50

Picture 2. KP Series Ozonators

KP Series ozonators (KORONA) are designed to extract ozone from atmosphere air and a given building or room. Ozone is formed here as a result of limar caron discharge. The distinguishing feature of KP series

ozonators is that they can operate at low temperatures and high humidity. The device is designed to produce ozonated water to irrigate plants. It can be used in drip irrigation systems [3].

Picture 3. Drip irrigation

Main advantages of technology. Experience has shown that the use of ozonated water to irrigate plants can increase productivity from 10% to 35%. The use of pronated water increases the, content of dissalved oxygen in the sail from 30% to 45%.By penetrating deep into the sail, watersoluble ozone is quickly converted to oxygen. Provedes the roots of plants with

the necessary respiratory regime and increases the availability of huntrients. Which leads to a decrease in the rate of application of fertilizers. Ozone has a high knee decontamination ability, which ensures the effective destruction of nematodes and other parasides in the soil.

Picture 4. Effects on the ozone system

The presence of dissolved oxygen levels in the soil increases the development of plant roots and prevents decay proceeded, in this way, we can visually see how the root systems, of the oxygenated area differ. No harmful residual elements are formed that must be removed other ozonation of water. The system of adding and supplying oxygen and ozone to irrigation water completes it on the basis of the existing pumping system [4].

Ozone is 15 times more soluble than dissolved oxygen. In the depths of the soil, ozone decomposes to oxygen and is separated from water. Plants need air to breathe. In anaerobic soils, anaerobic bacteria multiply, which slows plant growth and reduces productivity. Using ozonated water can increase productivity from 13% to 35% as it improves soil quality and plant health. From an agronomic point of view, the main advantage of ozone application is that. The concentration of oxygen in the water used to irrigate the root system of plants increases. Ozonation systems increase the amount of oxygen dissolved in water by 30-45%.

This system works with all types of water. The supply of irrigation water and the addition of ozone to it complement the existing pumping system. Irrigation is usually carried out at night. When evaporation is low. The gas mixture is added directly to the mains. Ozone kills all bacteria in irrigation water. Therefore, clean, biologically contaminated water is used for the walls. Ozone binds light metals such as iron and zinc around them to prevent them from combining with bicarbonates. This facilitates the assimilation of vital metals by the soil.

Ozone diffusion increases water-soluble oxygen by up to 400% , creating an aerobic environment. When the soil is irrigated with oxygen-rich water, positively charged ions are released calcium. The slows down the process of cation exchange in the soil, reduces the share of sodium in the exchange cations. Which significantly affects the agronomic characteristics of the soil, increasing its productivity [5].

Picture 5. Effects on the ozone system in soils

The two images were taken after a decision was made to irrigate the same area of the same province with ozone-rich oxygen-rich water 1 year apart.

Picture 6. Effects of ozone on microorganisms and toxins

Picture 7. Effects of ozone on toxins

Result.

1. Ozone eliminates harmful contaminants and bacteria, which facilitates the decomposition of unwanted organic materials.
2. Oxygen lies in aerobic conditions in the soil, which accelerates the development of the root system.
3. Reduces the toxicity of harmful substances in agricultural products.
4. Canning and preservation of agricultural products, as well as energy consumption until they are dried in the wet state, are of great importance in reducing losses during storage.

Referances

1. Van Veen J.A. Fate and activity of microorganisms introduced into soil. Microbiology and molecular biology rev., 1997, Vol. 61 №2.
2. International Ozone Association. <https://mozon.ru/ozonators/>.
3. Ozone and other environmentally friendly oxidizers. Moscow. Faculty of Chemistry, Moscow State University. 2012.
4. Lunin V.V., Samoilovich V.G., Tkachenko S.I. Theory and practice of obtaining and using ozone. From Moscow University, 2016.
5. Aliyev B.G. The basis of irrigated agriculture in Azerbaijan.